

Impact of Religiosity and Location on Risky Sexual Health Behaviour among Senior Secondary School Students

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of religiosity and location on risky sexual health behaviour among adolescent secondary school students. Two research questions were raised to guide the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. A simple random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and forty-five (345) participants of age 11-17 years, male and female students both in urban and rural areas. The reliability coefficient of the adolescent risky sexual behaviour scale is 0.89. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and T-test. The findings revealed that the independent variables of religiosity and location had a significant impact on adolescents' risky sexual health behaviour. The findings further revealed that urban adolescent students display higher sexual risky-taking behaviour than their rural resident counterparts, as divulged in the mean difference in the study. It was concluded that a proportion of adolescent secondary school students engaged in some form of risky sexual behaviour. However, it was recommended, among others, that in order to curtail or reduce early sexual initiation among adolescents, parents should begin early to teach or orientate their children on reproductive health matters.

Keywords: Religiosity, Location, Risky Sexual Behavior, Adolescents.

Introduction

Adolescents' problems are rooted in the background of their upbringing, which is the main cause of risky sexual behaviour which they exhibit within and outside society. The first contact in an adolescent's early life is the family, but the family has failed to do justice to the concept of sex education, which has led to numerous future challenges for the most promising youths today (Obro, 2020). Adolescents engage in risky sexual behaviour more often than other age-specific groups (Lewis et al., 2017; Ramiro et al., 2015). An essential aspect of healthy development, the transition from adolescence is marked by intense exploration of sexuality (Fortenberry, 2016). Despite region and cultures, including some evidence of high death rate of adolescents who have unprotected sexual intercourse, the prevalence of STIS remains the highest among young people,

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and the prevalence seems to be on the increase (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017). The risk of sexually transmitted infections (STIs) might build up over time if risky sexual habits established during youth have an impact on sexual behaviours in adulthood (Palmer et al., 2017).

Risky sexual behaviour is a major health issue in every society, and adolescents have been victims of sexually risky behaviours across several communities. The implication of adolescents engaging in risky sexual behaviour is beyond infections or contracting HIV and other kinds/forms of STDs, which may lead to death (Ogheneakoke & Obro, 2018). Since an adolescent student is characterized by psychological traits inherent in consolidating their interpersonal interactions with others, most of the students are at their adolescent age, and this period is marked by emotionality as a result of social change and expectations. To adjust well with other colleagues, adolescents need to possess positive attributes. Those with negative attributes may end up frustrated in school and miss their academic goal (Odojin & Okoh, 2023). The failures of sex education prompted the wrong signal, which is the risky behaviour exhibited by adolescents, which affects their reproductive system later in life. Apart from unwanted pregnancy resulting from unprotected sexual intercourse as an adolescent as a result of lack of sex education through the protracted stage of any of the deadly attractive diseases among the subject in question, which cannot be overemphasized due to complete lack of treatment to expunge all forms of diseases in the body of the adolescence (Nwalado, Obros & Ofuasia, 2006).

Sexual behaviour in this study refers to feelings of urge, seeking pleasure, sexual actions and reactions related to pleasure seeking. Sexual behaviour could be healthy or risky. Any romantic and pleasurable act or coitus that increases the chances of contracting sexually transmitted infections or becoming pregnant is risky sexual behaviour.

Risky sexual behaviours are activities that involve sex, which end with consequences that negatively affect in-school adolescents' health. Sexually dangerous behaviours such as oral and anal intercourse, having numerous sexual partners at once, not using protection, and engaging in unprotected sex are common among adolescents in school. Sexually transmitted diseases (STIs), including HIV/AIDS and sometimes infertility for life, unwanted pregnancies, and other harmful effects are linked to these activities. In this study context, risky sexual behaviour refers to all actions involving coitus or intercourse among in-school adolescents that may result in negative consequences to their health or may end in death.

Religion has been identified as a factor that has a strong influence on adolescent's risky sexual behaviour. Religious standards and beliefs can serve as a safeguard during adolescence against engaging in potentially harmful sexual behaviour. Numerous research have explicitly established the correlation between religion and both general behaviour and antisocial behaviour. Recent research conducted by Chen and Vanderweele (2018) has revealed that religious adolescents exhibit a decreased propensity for early sexual engagement and a higher likelihood of having a reduced number of partners. Nevertheless, religious standards can also heighten susceptibility to negative sexual consequences by discouraging young individuals from using condoms, both at the personal level (by embracing practices rooted in faith) and at the social level (by limiting access to comprehensive sexual education and STIS testing). As far as sexual behaviour is concerned, Odimegwu (2005) observed a relationship between religion and sexual attitude. McMillian (2011) found that "the religious group to which people identify appears to be substantially correlated with how they evaluate the appropriateness of premarital sexual behaviour and with the sexual morals they choose to follow in their own lives, including first sexual intercourse and less permissive attitudes about premarital sex". Several scholars have observed that adolescents who attached importance to religion were significantly more aware of the dangers of HIV/AIDS than their non-religious counterparts. They are more likely to delay sexual involvement than those with lower levels of religiosity (Hardy & Raffaelli, 2003; Shisana et al., 2008; Rostosky, Regnerus & Wright, 2003).

Research has exposed that religious beliefs can have a significant impact on adolescents' sexual attitude and behaviour in Nigeria. Adolescents who grow up in families with strict cultural and people who practise safer sexual activities and hold religious views about sex are more prone to postpone having their first sexual encounter (Babalola, 2019). Parents' religiosity can also affect adolescents' risky sexual behaviour. Supportive parents provide encouragement and emotional warmth to their child throughout adolescence and focus on spending time with the child and helping them by listening (Odojin & Urien, 2023). Higher levels of family religiosity may promote positive parent-child relationships by allowing parents and children to spend time together in a family-supportive environment, which in turn may reduce the likelihood that an adolescent will have sex (Pearce & Axinn, 1998; Abbott-Chapman & Denholm, 2001, Regnerus & Burdette, 2006).

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Location has also been recognised as a determinant that has a strong influence on adolescents' risky sexual behaviour. Extensive research has consistently proven that urban dwellers possess greater awareness regarding HIV/AIDS prevention, thereby increasing their likelihood of engaging in condom usage compared to rural inhabitants. Moreover, metropolitan locations have a greater likelihood of having multiple regular sexual partners and contracting sexually transmitted illnesses compared to rural locales (Ntozi et al., 2000; Peltzer, 2010). Karim et al. (2003) found that residence in a rural setting was associated with an increased probability of having had sex among males, while females residing in small towns were significantly more likely than their counterparts residing in cities or large towns to have had multiple recent partners. In contrast, a study conducted by Kwankye (2005) discovered that the proportion of sexually active participants was higher in the urban area compared to the rural district.

However, having assessed the whole lots of predicaments experienced by adolescents, it is worth the necessity to educate the people around the sine through the process of enlightening the adolescents and with the great burden in me to share these core values of life which triggered my burning desire to embark on this theme to be studied.

Research Questions

1. What is the impact of religiosity on risky sexual behaviour among adolescent secondary school students?
2. To what extent does difference in location influence risky sexual behaviour among adolescent secondary school students?

Methodology

Research designs are perceived to be an overall strategy adopted by the researcher whereby different components of the study are integrated logically to effectively address a research problem. In this study, the researcher employed the survey research design. The population consists of all secondary school students in Isoko-North local government area of Delta State. There are 14 secondary schools in Isoko-North Local Government Area of Delta State. The study adopted the simple random sampling method to select three hundred and forty-five students.

The research instrument used in this study is the questionnaire. A 10-minute survey containing 19 questions was administered to the enrolled participants. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. The first section enquired about the respondents' demographic or

personal data, while the second section was in line with the study objectives aimed at providing answers to the research questions. The reliability and validity of the research instrument were determined. The Pearson Correlation Coefficient was utilized to determine the reliability of the instrument. The research instrument was found to be relatively dependable with a coefficient value of 0.68. According to (Taber, 2017), the range of reasonable reliability is between 0.67 and 0.87. The responses were analysed using the frequency tables, which provided answers to the research questions.

Results

RQ1: What is the impact of religiosity on sexual behaviour among adolescent secondary school students?

Table 1: Relationship between Religion and Risky Sexual Behaviour

(n = 345)										
S/N	Religion and sexual behaviour	Always		Sometimes		Rarely		Never		
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
1	Risky sexual behaviour	-	-	0	0.0	7	13.0	47	87.0	
	Islam	-	-	1	0.4	20	7.0	263	92.6	
	Christianity	-	-	0.	0.0	0	0.0	7	100.0	
	Traditional Cluster percentage	0.1		6.66		93.2				
		$\chi^2value = 3.011, d.f = 4, p-value = .556$								
2	Possession of multiple sexual partners									
	Islam	2	3.7	5	9.3	7.	13.0	40	24.1	
	Christianity	6	2.1	7	2.5	31	10.9	240	84.5	
	Traditional	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	7	100.0	
	Cluster percentage	1.9		3.9		7.96		86.2		
		$\chi^2value = 8.728, d.f = 4, p-value = .189$								
3	Having Sex Under Intoxication									
	Islam	0	0.0	4	7.4	7	13.0	43	79.6	
	Christianity	1	0.4	10	3.5	20	7.0	253	89.1	
	Traditional	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	7	100.0	
	Cluster percentage	0.1		3.6		6.66		89.56		
		$\chi^2value = 5.67, d.f = 4, p-value = .498$								
4	Unprotected sex									
	Islam	2	3.7	2	3.7	14	25.9	36	66.7	
	Christianity	1	0.4	17	6.0	49	17.3	217	76.4	
	Traditional	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	7	100.0	
	Cluster percentage	1.36		3.21		4.4		81.0		

		χ^2 value = 11.066, d.f = 4, p-value = .086			
5	Transactional/Survival Sex				
	Islam	0 0.0	4 7.4	6 11.1	44 81.5
	Christianity	3 1.1	6 2.1	22 7.7	253 89.1
	Traditional	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	7 100.0
	Cluster percentage	0.36	3.16	6.26	90.2
		χ^2 value = 6.865, d.f = 4, p-value = .334			
6	Oral Sex				
	Islam	4 7.4	5 9.3	1 1.9	44 81.5
	Christianity	6 2.1	19 6.7	5 1.8	254 89.4
	Traditional	0 0.0	1 14.3	0 0.0	6 85.7
	Cluster percentage	3.16	10.1	12.3	85.5
		χ^2 value = 5.954, df =4, p-value = .428			
7	Anal Sex				
	Islam	3 5.6	4 7.4	1 1.9	46 85.2
	Christianity	4 1.4	8 2.8	4 1.4	268 94.4
	Traditional	0 0.0	0 0.0	0 0.0	7 100.0
	Cluster percentage	2.3	3.4	1.1	93.2
	Overall Cluster % Total	(P-Value 0.045)			
		χ^2 Value = 7.602, df = 4, p – value = .269			

Table 1 shows no relationship between religiosity and risky sexual behaviour of the respondents: sexual behaviour (χ^2 3.011, p-value = .556), possession of multiple sexual partners (χ^2 = 8.728, p-value = .189), having sex under intoxication (χ^2 = 5.367, p-value = .498), unprotected sex (χ^2 = 11.066, p-value = .086), transactional/survival sex (χ^2 = 6.865, p-value .334), oral sex (χ^2 = 5.954, p-value = .428), and anal sex (χ^2 = 7.602, p-value = .269), since the p – values are greater than .05 level of significance at 4 degrees of freedom. Therefore, there is no relationship between religiosity and risky sexual behaviour among adolescents.

RQ2: What is the relationship between the location of in-school adolescents and their sexual behaviour?

Table 2: Analysis showing the difference in location and risky sexual behaviour.

S/N	Location and Sexual Behaviour	Always		Sometimes		Rarely		Never	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
1	Risky Sexual Behaviour								
	Urban	-	-	1	0.4	15	5.8	241	93.8
	Rural	-	-	0	0.0	12	13.6	76	86.4

	Cluster percentage	- 0.2 9.7 98.1			
		χ^2 Value = 5.830, d.f = 2, p-value = .054 (No relationship)			
2	Possession of Multiple Sexual Partners				
	Urban	5 1.9	5 1.9	18 7.0	229 89.1
	Rural	3 3.4	7 8.0	20 22.7	58 65.9
	Cluster percentage	2.65 4.95 14.85 77.5			
		χ^2 Value = 26.364, d.f = 2, p-value = .000 (Relationship)			
3	Having Sex Under Intoxication				
	Urban	1 0.4	6 2.3	10 3.9	240 93.4
	Rural	0 0.0	8 9.1	17 19.3	63 71.6
	Cluster percentage	0.2 5.7 11.6 82.5			
		χ^2 Value = 31.197, d.f = 2, p-value = .000 (Relationship)			
4	Unprotected Sex				
	Urban	2 0.8	10 3.9	32 12.5	213 82.9
	Rural	1 1.1	9 10.2	31 35.2	47 53.4
	Cluster percentage	0.95 7.05 23.85 68.15			
		χ^2 Value = 31.052, d.f = 2, p-value = .000* (Relationship)			
5	Transactional/Survival Sex				
	Urban	2 0.8	4 1.6	14 5.4	237 92.2
	Rural	1 1.1	6 6.8	14 15.9	67 76.1
	Cluster percentage	0.95 4.2 10.65 84.15			
		χ^2 Value = 17.122, d.f = 2, p-value = .001 (Relationship)			
6	Oral Sex				
	Urban	6. 2.3	14 5.4	3 1.2	234 91.1
	Rural	4 4.5	11 12.5	3 3.4	70 79.5
	Cluster percentage	3.4 8.95 2.3 85.3			
		χ^2 Value = 8.484, d.f = 2, p-value = .037 (Relationship)			
7	Anal Sex				
	Urban	5 1.9	5 1.9	2 0.8	245 95.3
	Rural	2 2.3	7 8.0	3 3.4	76 86.4
	Cluster percentage	2.1 4.95 2.1 90.85			
	Overall Cluster % Total	(P-Value 0.015)			
		χ^2 Value = 10.537, d.f = 2, p-value = .015 (Relationship)			

Table 2 shows a relationship between location and risky sexual behaviour as follows: possession of multiple sexual partner ($\chi^2 = 26.364$, p-value = .000), sex under intoxication ($\chi^2 = 31.197$, p-value = .000), unprotected sex ($\chi^2 = 31.052$, p-value = .000), transactional/survival sex ($\chi^2 = 17.122$, p-value = .001), oral sex ($\chi^2 = 8.484$, p-value = .037), and anal sex ($\chi^2 = 10.537$, p-value = .015), since the p-values are less than .05 level of significance at two degrees of freedom. Furthermore, the Table shows no relationship between location and sexual behaviour ($\chi^2 = 5.830$, p-value = .054) since the p-value is greater than the .05 level of significance at two degrees of freedom.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings revealed no relationship between religiosity and risky sexual behaviours. This reason could be that the religious group with which people identify looks to be substantially associated with how they evaluate the appropriateness of premarital sexual behaviour and with the sexual morals they choose to follow in their lives. Adolescents who follow a religious faith may exhibit a reduced propensity for early engagement in sexual activities and a higher likelihood of having relatively few sexual partners. Another factor may be that strong family religious beliefs can foster satisfactory parent-child relationships by enabling parents and children to spend more time together in a nurturing family setting, so decreasing the probability of an adolescent participating in risky sexual activities. The present discovery aligns with the observations made by Odimegwu (2005), who identified a correlation between religion and sexual views. Research conducted by McMillian (2011) revealed that the religious convictions held by parents exerted a substantial influence on the sexual conduct of teenagers.

The second study showed that adolescents' risky sexual behaviour differs significantly depending on where they live (rural and urban). This is due to the possibility that urban teenagers are more aware of HIV/AIDS preventive strategies and are more likely to use condoms than their rural counterparts. In addition, metropolitan areas have greater rates of sexually transmitted infections and multiple regular sexual partners than rural ones. This is consistent with research by Karim et al. (2003), which showed that living in a rural area was linked to a higher likelihood of having had sex for men and that women living in small towns were substantially more likely to have had multiple recent partners than women living in cities or large towns. On the other hand, a

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study by Kwankye (2005) discovered that the urban area had a larger percentage of individuals who were sexually active than the rural district.

Conclusion

The study ascertained that a proportion of in-school adolescents involve themselves in some forms of risky sexual behaviour, like early sexual initiation, possession of multiple sexual associates/partners, and having sex under intoxication, among others. The study concluded that religiosity has a significant or substantial impact on adolescents in secondary schools and that location did significantly determine in-school adolescents' risky sexual behaviour.

Recommendation

1. Reproductive health /sexuality education should be incorporated into secondary school curriculum/syllabus where not done.
2. School authorities and teachers should develop comprehensive lesson plans/notes on reproductive health/sexuality education based on differences in adolescents' religion and location.
3. To curtail or reduce adolescents early sexual initiation, parents should begin early to teach or orientate their children on reproductive health matters.
4. There is a need for religious bodies, institutions or organizations to control risky sexual behaviours by setting rules to regulate adolescents' risky sexual behaviours through moral order, sanctions and punishments by deities for deviant adolescents.
5. Thorough sensitization and core orientation towards sex education must be given to all adolescents both in the urban and rural areas and in the four walls of the classroom and the community at large. Parents have to play a fundamental or cicial role in educating their children, including the school counsellor, by organizing regular educational programmes that will lead to a positive turnaround in the avoidance of sexually risky behaviour.

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